

Global Warming Forecast over the Land and over the Ocean

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Abstract

This publication analyzes 12 options for forecasting Global Warming over the Land (GWL) and Global Warming over the Ocean (GWO).

The trendlines' parameters are related to the Global Warming over the land+ocean (GW):

- GWL/GW
- GWO/GW
- GWL-GW
- GWO-GW

The trendline types are:

- linear
- parabolic
- power

The periods considered for the trendlines are:

- 1940-2021
- 1977-2021

The determination of the best option considered Mean Squared Error – R^2 and the proximity to the average of GWL in 2100 of all options.

The optimum option is the GWO/GW power trendline in the range 1940-2021.

The calculations also involve the area of the land and the ocean of the Earth with 31.18% applied to the land.

The forecast for Global Warming over the Land for 2100 is 6.5°C and over the Ocean 3.4°C above the 1850-1900 baseline.

Glossary

AL	Total area of the Land, %
AO	Total area of the Ocean, %
Ave	average
BL	baseline of surface temperature change (GW) 1850-1900
BAU	Business as Usual
GW	Global Warming, global surface temperature above the 1850-1900 baseline, land+ocean, °C
GWL	global surface temperature over the land only, above the 1850-1900 baseline, °C
GWO	global surface temperature over the ocean only, above the 1850-1900 baseline, °C
TL	trendline

Business As Usual Scenario

All calculations and estimations in this work are for the Business As Usual (BAU) scenario, the effectiveness of the future CO₂ emissions mitigation will be as in the past.

Global Warming Baseline

All Global Warming data in this publication are above the 1850-1900 baseline, °C.

Global Warming Dataset

The dataset of global surface temperature changes for land and ocean (GW) converted to 1850-1900 baseline is publicly available on [1]. The dataset is based on NASA [2] [3], NOAA [4], and Berkley Earth [5] [6]. All temperatures are in Celsius (°C).

Global Warming Forecast

Global Warming forecast over the land+ocean (GW) above the 1850-1900 baseline is publically available on [7].

Global Warming over the Land+Ocean and over the Land only

Chart 1 - GW Land+Ocean and Land only (GWL) 1850-2021, °C [1]

Global Warming over the Land+Ocean and over the Ocean only

Chart 2 - GW Land+Ocean and Ocean only (GWO) 1880-2021, °C [1]

Land and Ocean Area

Global Warming of the Earth (GW) is the result of Global Warming over the Land (GWL) and Global Warming over the Ocean (GWO).

Formula 1 - Correlation between GWL and GWO according to Land and Ocean area

$$\mathbf{GW = GWL * AL + GWO * AO}$$

GW	Global Warming of the Earth, °C
GWL	Global Warming over the Land, °C
GWO	Global Warming over the Ocean, °C
AL	Total area of the Land, %
AO	Total area of the Ocean, %

$$\mathbf{AL + AO = 100\%}$$

$$\mathbf{AL = (GW - GWO) / (GWL - GWO)}$$

$$\mathbf{AO = 100\% - AL}$$

Based on the Global Warming data, the average land area (AL) in the period 1990-2021 was 31.18% of the total area of the Earth, and the ocean area (AO) was 68.82%.

Calculation of GWL

Formula 1 may be applied to determine Global Warming over the Land (GWL).

$$\mathbf{GW = GWL*AL + GWO*AO}$$

Formula 2 - Determination of GWL

$$\mathbf{GWL = (GW - GWO*AO) / AL}$$

Parameters Considered for Determination of GWL and GWO

1. GWL/GW
2. GWO/GW
3. GWL- GW
4. GWO-GW

Types of Trendline

For parameters 1 and 2 (GWL/GW) and (GLO/GW) linear and power trendlines give reasonable results, therefore, both trendlines will be analyzed.

For parameters 3 and 4 linear and parabolic trendlines give reasonable results, therefore, both trendlines will be analyzed.

List of Options which will be Analyzed in this Work

1. GWL/GW linear trendline
2. GWL/GW power trendline
3. GWO/GW linear trendline
4. GWO/GW power trendline
5. GWL-GW linear trendline
6. GWL-GW parabolic trendline
7. GWO-GW linear trendline
8. GWO-GW parabolic trendline

Option 1: GWL/GW Linear Trendline

Chart 3 - GWL/GW 1850-2021 [1]

The above chart shows unreasonable results for the GWL/GW ratio before the year 1940. The next chart is limited to the years 1940-2021.

Chart 4 - GWL/GW 1940-2021

Also this chart shows unreasonable results before 1977.

Chart 5 - Option 1: GWL/GW 1977-2021 Linear Trendline

Table 1 - Option 1: Linear trendline of GWL/GW in years 1977-2021

a	0.003769691567
b	1.345076264580
R2	0.188

Chart 6 - Option 1: GWL/GW 1977-2021 Linear Trendline

Table 2 - Option1: Global Warming over the Land forecast for 2100

year	GW	GWL/GW	GWL
2100	4.407	1.835	8.088

Option 2: GWL/GW Power Trendline

Chart 7 - Option 2: GWL/GW 1977-2021 Power Trendline

Table 3 - Option 2: Power trendline of GWL/GW in years 1977-2021

k	1.143647496348
p	0.073000514630
R2	0.219

Table 4 - Option2: Global Warming over the Land forecast for 2100

year	GW	GWL/GW	GWL
2100	4.407	1.632	7.191

Option 3: GWO/GW Linear Trendline

The periods analyzed in Options 1 and 2 were:

- o 1850-2021
- o 1940-2021
- o 1977-2021

The same periods will be considered in all other options.

Chart 8 - GWO/GW 1880-2021

The above chart shows unreasonable results for the GWO/GW ratio before the year 1940. The next chart is limited to the years 1940-2021.

Chart 9 - Option 3: GWO/GW 1940-2021 Linear Trendline

Table 5 - Option 3: GWO/GW 1940-2021 Linear Trendline

a	-0.002417400330
b	0.958565501121
R2	0.129

GWL is calculated with Formula 2:

$$\mathbf{GWL = (GW - GWO*AO) / AL}$$

Table 6 - Option3: Global Warming over the Land forecast for 2100

year	GW	GWO/GW	GWO	GWL
2100	4.407	0.572	2.520	8.572

Chart 10 - GWO/GW 1977-2021 Linear Trendline

The above chart shows unreasonable results for the year 2100, therefore, it will be not considered.

Option 4: GWO/GW Power Trendline

Chart 11 - Option 4-1: GWO/GW 1940-2021 Power Trendline

Table 7 - Option 4-1: GWO/GW 1940-2021 Power Trendline

k	0.992427705218
p	-0.046868903112
R2	0.058

Table 8 - Option 4-1: Global Warming over the Land forecast for 2100

year	GW	GWO/GW	GWO	GWL
2100	4.407	0.782	3.448	6.524

Chart 12 - Option 4-2: GWO/GW 1977-2021 Power Trendline

Table 9 - Option 4-2: GWO/GW 1977-2021 Power Trendline

k	1.294982853918
p	-0.144426000406
R2	0.517

Table 10 - Option 4-2: Global Warming over the Land forecast for 2100

year	GW	GWO/GW	GWO	GWL
2100	4.407	0.641	2.826	7.897

Option 5: GWL-GW Linear Trendline

Chart 13 - GWL-GW 1850-2021 [1]

Chart 14 - Option 5: GWL-GW 1977-2021 Linear Trendline

Table 11 - Option 5: GWL-GW 1977-2021 Linear Trendline

a	0.010869131533
b	0.063540868833
R2	0.719

Table 12 - Option 5: Global Warming over the Land forecast for 2100

year	GW	GWL-GW	GWL
2100	4.407	1.477	5.884

Option 6: GWL-GW Parabolic Trendline

Chart 15 - Option 6-1: GWL-GW 1940-2021 Parabolic Trendline

Table 13 - Option 6-1: GWL-GW 1940-2021 Parabolic Trendline

a	0.000128255319
b	-0.005005870389
c	0.207601974179
R2	0.713

Table 14 - Option 6-1: Global Warming over the Land forecast for 2100

year	GW	GWL-GW	GWL
2100	4.407	2.690	7.097

Chart 16 - Option 6-2: GWL-GW 1977-2021 Parabolic Trendline

Table 15 - Option 6-2: GWL-GW 1977-2021 Parabolic Trendline

a	-0.000009602797
b	0.011445299327
c	0.056518023609
R2	0.719

Table 16 - Option 6-2: Global Warming over the Land forecast for 2100

year	GW	GWL-GW	GWL
2100	4.407	1.382	5.789

Option 7: GWO-GW Linear Trendline

Formula 3 - Determination of GWL according to GWO-GW Trendline

$$\mathbf{GW = GWL*AL + GWO*AO}$$

$$\mathbf{GWL = (GW - GWO*AO) / AL}$$

$$\mathbf{AL = 31.18402946\%}$$

$$\mathbf{AO = 68.81597054\%}$$

GW	Global Warming Forecast in year y as in publication [1], °C
GWL	Global Warming over the Land, °C
GWO	Global Warming over the Ocean, °C
AL	Total area of the Land, %
AO	Total area of the Ocean, %

Chart 17 - GWO-GW 1980-2021 [1]

Chart 18 - Option 7-1: GWO-GW 1940-2021 Linear Trendline

Table 17 - Option 7-1: GWO-GW 1940-2021 Linear Trendline

a	-0.003730388582
b	0.048544866004
R2	0.643

Table 18 - Option 7-1: Global Warming over the Land forecast for 2100

year	GW	GWO-GW	GWO	GWL
2100	4.407	-0.548	3.859	5.617

Chart 19 - Option 7-2: GWO-GW 1977-2021 Linear Trendline

Table 19 - Option 7-2: GWO-GW 1977-2021 Linear Trendline

a	-0.007044883619
b	0.039787249305
R2	0.796

Table 20 - Option 7-2: Global Warming over the Land forecast for 2100

year	GW	GWO-GW	GWO	GWL
2100	4.407	-0.876	3.531	6.340

Option 8: GWO-GW Parabolic Trendline

Chart 20 - Option 8-1: GWO-GW 1940-2021 Parabolic Trendline

Table 21 - Option 8-1: GWO-GW 1940-2021 Parabolic Trendline

a	-0.000085639629
b	0.003377700633
c	-0.050968383017
R2	0.795

Table 22 - Option 8-1: Global Warming over the Land forecast for 2100

year	GW	GWO-GW	GWO	GWL
2100	4.407	-1.703	2.704	8.165

Chart 21 - Option 8-2: GWO-GW 1977-2021 Parabolic Trendline

Table 23 - Option 8-2: GWO-GW 1977-2021 Parabolic Trendline

a	-0.000019946252
b	-0.005848108519
c	0.025199890587
R2	0.797

Table 24 - Option 8-2: Global Warming over the Land forecast for 2100

year	GW	GWO-GW	GWO	GWL
2100	4.407	-1.072	3.335	6.773

Trendlines Results

Table 25 - Trendline Options' results

Option	Parameter	Trendline	From	R2	GWL in 2100 °C
Option 1	GWL/GW	Linear	1977	0.188	8.088
Option 2	GWL/GW	Power	1977	0.219	7.191
Option 3	GWO/GW	Linear	1940	0.129	8.572
Option 4-1	GWO/GW	Power	1940	0.058	6.524
Option 4-2	GWO/GW	Power	1977	0.517	7.897
Option 5	GWL-GW	Linear	1977	0.719	5.884
Option 6-1	GWL-GW	Parabolic	1940	0.713	7.097
Option 6-2	GWL-GW	Parabolic	1977	0.719	5.789
Option 7-1	GWO-GW	Linear	1940	0.643	5.617
Option 7-2	GWO-GW	Linear	1977	0.796	6.340
Option 8-1	GWO-GW	Parabolic	1940	0.795	8.165
Option 8-2	GWO-GW	Parabolic	1977	0.797	6.773
Ave				0.524	6.995
Min				0.058	5.617
Max				0.797	8.572
12	Count				

Optimization of the Results

Two variables will be included in the optimization:

- Accuracy of the trendlines based on R2 – Mean Squared Error as displayed on the xls chart
- Proximity to the average of all options in this work

As the trendline accuracy is more important than the average approach, the trendline accuracy has a weight of 60% and the proximity to the average 40%.

Table 26 - Optimization results

Option	Parameter	Trendline	From	R2	To Ave	Σ
Option 1	GWL/GW	Linear	1977	195%	46%	242%
Option 2	GWL/GW	Power	1977	228%	41%	269%
Option 3	GWO/GW	Linear	1940	135%	49%	184%
Option 4-1	GWO/GW	Power	1940	60%	37%	97%
Option 4-2	GWO/GW	Power	1977	538%	45%	584%
Option 5	GWL-GW	Linear	1977	749%	34%	782%
Option 6-1	GWL-GW	Parabolic	1940	742%	41%	783%
Option 6-2	GWL-GW	Parabolic	1977	749%	33%	782%
Option 7-1	GWO-GW	Linear	1940	670%	32%	702%
Option 7-2	GWO-GW	Linear	1977	829%	36%	865%
Option 8-1	GWO-GW	Parabolic	1940	828%	47%	875%
Option 8-2	GWO-GW	Parabolic	1977	830%	39%	868%

The most accurate trendline is Option 4-1. It also has the best optimization score.

Determination of GWO in 2100

Formula 1 may be applied to determine Global Warming over the Ocean (GWO).

$$\mathbf{GW = GWL*AL + GWO*AO}$$

$$\mathbf{GWO = (GW - GWL*AL) / AO}$$

The Selected Option

Table 27 - Selected Option

ID	Option 4-1
Parameter	GWO/GW
Trendline	Power
from	1940
to	2021
k	0.992427705218
p	-0.046868903112
R2	0.0576
GWL in 2030, °C	2.15
GWO in 2030, °C	1.20
GWL in 2100, °C	6.52
GWO in 2100, °C	3.45

Chart 22 - BAU forecast 2020-2100 using the selected trendline: Option 4-1: GWO/GW 1940-2021 Power Trendline

Paris Agreement GW Target of 1.5°C

According to [7] in the BAU scenario Global Warming of 1.5°C will occur in 2030.

Table 28 - GWL and GWO in GW=1.5°C year (2030)

	GW	GWL	GWO
2020	1.24	1.76	1.00
2030	1.50	2.15	1.20
2100	4.41	6.52	3.45

Paris Agreement Global Warming target of 1.5°C involves Global Warming over the Land (GWL) of 2.15°C and over the Ocean (GWO) of 1.2°C.

Dataset of GWL and GWO Forecast

The dataset of Global Warming over the Land (GWL) and Global Warming over the Ocean (GWO) forecast according to this work is available in publication [8].

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